

National and International Wood Policy

5 May 2026

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The rationale for a wood policy dialogue

National developments and processes

Austrian Forest Fund

www.waldfonds.at

Total volume of 430 million euros

- Largest investment package for the Austrian forestry and timber industry (1 February 2021)

Objectives of the forest fund

- Compensation for loss of value caused by bark beetle damage
- Reduction of bark beetle infestation
- Developing climate-resilient forests and strengthening biodiversity in forests
- **Strengthening the use of wood as a raw material as an active contribution to climate protection**

Response to challenges: Austrian Forest Fund (430 Mio. €)

1. Reforestation and tending measures after damage events
2. Development of climate-fit forests
3. Compensation for loss of value caused by bark beetle damage
4. Establishment of wet and dry deposits of damaged wood
5. Mechanical debarking and other preventive forest protection measures
6. Forest fire prevention measures
7. Research measures and research infrastructure for the production of wood gas and biofuels
8. Research measures on the issue of "climate-fit forests"
9. Measures to intensify the use of wood as a raw material
10. Measures to promote biodiversity in forests

**Austrian
Wood Initiative**

Austrian Wood Initiative

Innovation

- **Currently 30 research projects funded (> € 20 mio.)**
- Research themes:
 - Digitalization and AI
 - Hybrid materials with wood
 - Circular building solutions
 - Hardwood products
 - Carbon sequestration modelling, etc.
- **Planned Calls Innovation:**
 - Q2 2026 with a budget of approx. €3.6 million
 - Thematic areas: LCA, digitalisation of supply chains, timber construction systems

See all projects here:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLEGQEle016TTcZILrqi9VjhJGJOZodfwd>

International developments and processes

The European Wood Policy Platform (WoodPoP)

- initiated by **Austria** and **Finland** in 2021
- facilitates the **exchange and collaboration** between administration, industry and research
- advocates the **role of wood** as a renewable resource
- Secretariat **hosted by IUFRO** and financed by Austria

Develop **wood-related policy solutions, measures and recommendations**

Shape the **frameworks for sustainable wood-based value chains**

Stimulate **innovation and exchange**

Increase visibility of the **added value of enhanced wood use**

The WoodPoP structure

High Level Meeting
(HLM)

Main **decision-making**
body
political level

Supported by the **woodPoP Secretariat** hosted in
IUFRO

Expert Group
Meeting (EGM)

Main **forum of exchange**
operational level

Technical Working
Groups (TWGs)

Governance

Building

Innovation and Research

Education and
Vocational Training

Communication

Informal Steering
Group (ISG)

Austria, Finland,
Germany, Switzerland,
Slovenia, Czech Republic,
Norway, Luxemburg and
Ireland

Technical working groups

TECHNICAL WORKING GROUPS

SIGN-UP for a TECHNICAL WORKING GROUP:
<https://woodpop.eu/>

Governance

Wood-related policy recommendations, Policy Paper outreach

LEAD: AT

Building

Use of wood in construction, Green public procurement and Interlinkages between wood and health

LEAD: DE

Innovation & Research

Overcoming the valley of death for innovation, Innovation guide

LEAD: CH & LUX

Education & Vocational Training

Qualification along the wood-based value chain, Development of a Policy Brief

LEAD: SI

Communication & Information

Preparatory work for a European Wood Building Prize, Information leaflet

LEAD: CZ & IE

Technical Working Groups

Governance (Lead: AT)	Wood Policy Lab „ Evaluation and evolution of WoodPop “, 20-22 April 2026, Tulln Policy Paper on „ Is there enough Wood “, September 2026 9 Expert Group Meeting , 15 September 2026 V. High-level meeting , Prague CZ, November 2026
Building (Lead: DE, FI)	Online Webinar: “ Circular Timber Buildings and Construction ” 16. April 2026 Subgroup on Eurocode 5 Subgroup on Health and Well-being of timber constructions : Policy Paper, May 2026
Innovation and Research (Lead: CH,LUX)	Task Force 1: Bridging the Valley of Death in Wood Innovation Task Force 2: Financing Innovations in the Wood Sector Task Force 3: Influencing FP10 and EU policy/programming Prolog V Innovation at International timber construction forum Innsbruck, December 2026
Education and vocational training (Lead: SI)	Praparing woodPoP Student Award Mapping the wood related programs in Europe
Communication and information (Lead: CZ, IR)	WoodPoP Dara Award – Submission 22 April 2026 Public voting and Hall of Fame – Showcasing excellence in Europe’s timber architecture Award Ceremony in Prague (CZ) on 26 November 2026

**Scan to access
The Policy Paper
in 6 different languages**

European Wood Policy Platform | Policy Paper 2024

A WOOD-BASED CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY FOR A SUSTAINABLE EUROPE

GREEN CONSTRUCTION AND INNOVATIVE
WOOD SOLUTIONS

A wood-based circular bioeconomy for a sustainable Europe

- 1 Wood Sourcing and Supply Chain Management
- 2 Circular Utilization
- 3 Wood Processing and Manufacturing
- 4 Construction and Buildings
- 5 Develop Smart and Novel Wood Uses
- 6 Skills and Education
- 7 Communication and Awareness
- 8 Governance: Regulatory Compliance, Harmonisation, and Circularity

Publications

Publications

Technical Brief
June 2024

FIRE SAFE BUILDING WITH WOOD

Executive statement

Modern engineered wood products and engineering techniques can now be used to construct large and complex timber buildings.

The concerns on fire safety of timber buildings relate to the nature of wood being a relatively lightweight and natural biomaterial compared with buildings of non-combustible materials.

Key messages

The topic of fire safety is gathering increasing interest, as the current fire codes and regulations have been conceived for other building materials.

To be most effective, fire prevention considerations and possible risks need to be considered at the design stage.

Human safety in wood buildings is assured. Methods to prevent and limit spread of fire are compartmentation, automatic extinguishing, and if needed, limiting areas of visible wood. In exit routes, any combustibles must be limited in all buildings.

Background

This brief was commissioned by the Technical Working Group 'Building' of the **European Wood Policy Platform (woodPoP)**.

woodPoP provides a dedicated forum for multilateral policy, knowledge, and experience exchange between public and private actors from the wood sector for developing policy solutions at the national and regional levels. It focuses on developing frameworks for sustainable wood-based value chains and their contribution to an innovative, circular bioeconomy.

Policy Brief
May 2025

The Wood-Based Sector Requires a Skilled Workforce to Propel Europe Towards a Sustainable Future

Background

The wood-based sector (WBS), with 8 million employees¹ is a **key player in the transition towards a more innovative, inclusive, and sustainable society**, specifically contributing to rural development and the job creation, considering primary and secondary raw materials processing and off-site prefabrication.²

To advance **circular thinking, eco-design, and actions across all stages of processing and product service life**, there is a need to enhance the reuse of the relevant product system and its materials, ensuring the efficient use of wood as a renewable and valuable resource. **Wood-based construction (WBC)** is the most apparent part of the WBS to showcase these efforts, as its products store biogenically sequestered carbon throughout their service life³.

¹Economic Impact of the Forestry and Wood Industry in Europe - WoodPoP
²https://www.woodpop.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/CI04-24_WoodPoP_Policy_Paper_2024_1.pdf
³https://www.woodpop.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/CI04-24_WoodPoP_Policy_Paper_2024_1.pdf

4th High Level Meeting of the European Wood Policy Platform (WoodPoP)

15 October 2025, Izola, Slovenia

Outcome Statement

'The role of wood in Europe's clean, just and competitive transformation'

The Fourth High Level Meeting affirms that:

1. Wood and wood-based products are strategic and renewable resources that offer immediate and scalable solutions to **mitigate and adapt to climate change, decarbonise the built environment, strengthen Europe's economic resilience, and foster social cohesion**:
 - **Sustainable forest management** is a prerequisite for providing the renewable resource wood and is key to securing forest ecosystem services in the long term.
 - Wood products are **highly versatile, store carbon throughout their lifecycle**, and offer sustainable alternatives to non-renewable and fossil-intensive materials and fuels.
 - The forestry and the wood industries generate a **total gross value added of €1,114 billion** across Europe¹.
 - With **17.5 million jobs** supported across the value chain² this industry is a cornerstone of economic transformation, job creation and inclusive growth in both urban and rural areas.
2. Wood is a catalyst for **innovation, sustainable construction and many multifunctional uses**:
 - Timber buildings act as long-term **carbon sinks**, have the potential to reduce energy demand for heating and cooling, and enhance **human health and well-being**.

¹Source: Econmve, Economica (2023): The economic impact of the forestry and wood industry in Europe in terms of bioeconomy, Vienna; Europe is understood as including EU-27, Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom

²This includes the forestry and wood industry directly as well as their extensive network of suppliers, primary and secondary raw materials processing and off-site prefabrication Source: Econmve, Economica (2023)

Extended Technical Brief

Public Procurement for Wooden Buildings

September 2025

Technical Working Group Building
Subgroup on Public Procurement

Funded by the Austrian Federal Fund, an initiative of the Austrian Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Climate and Environmental Protection, Regions and Water Management (BMLFUW).

Available at woodpop.eu
E-Mail us at contact@woodpop.eu

Publications

Policy Brief
November 2025.

Wood for Europe's future: FP10 as the engine of decarbonisation and competitiveness

To harness the full strategic potential of Europe's forests and wood resources for the green, digital, and circular transitions, FP10 must embed wood science, technology, and innovation across all pillars. Coordinated investment in research excellence, industrial innovation, and skills development, prioritising the needs of SMEs, will strengthen resilience, accelerate decarbonisation, strengthen existing markets and unlock new markets. By integrating wood research infrastructures into European networks, fostering cross-sector collaboration, and aligning with New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles as well as EU Missions, Europe can position its forest-based industries as global leaders in sustainability and competitiveness. This is not only an environmental imperative but a socio-economic opportunity that demands decisive policy support and funding. Europe must act now.

WoodPoP call for actions

WoodPoP calls for urgent, coordinated action under FP10 to unlock the full potential of Europe's forestry and wood sector, a cornerstone for resilience, growth, climate neutrality and decarbonisation, circularity, and resilience. Despite being a vast, nationally available, reliable, renewable bioresource, it remains underused in terms of value added. Six priority challenges demand attention: Economic growth, climate adaptation, decarbonisation, digital traceability, inclusive governance, and skills development.

FP10 must drive research and innovation across its four pillars to scale low-carbon construction, develop circular wood systems, advance climate-smart and sustainable forestry, and deploy digital solutions for transparency. Europe cannot afford to miss this opportunity. FP10 must lead the way to enable a secure and scaling wood-based value chains as engines of competitiveness, social resilience and climate action.

Rationale

Wood is one of Europe's most strategic renewable resources, vital for regenerative growth and decarbonisation through carbon storage in solid wood, wood-based products, and biocomposites. The European wood sector contributes with € 1.114 billion significantly to EU's GDP and employs about 17.5 million people (Ecomove, 2023). Basis economic data to the value chains of [Forestry and Wood Industry in Europe](#). Fully aligned with the 'One Health' approach, the wood sector supports environmental, social, and economic sustainability, yet it remains underexploited in EU industry and climate strategies. This policy brief translates the [WoodPoP Policy Paper](#) into actionable recommendations for FP10 to accelerate research and innovation, strengthen the circular bioeconomy, and position wood at the core of resilient value chains and low-carbon construction:

Key recommendations for Horizon Europe 2028 – 2034

Strategic decisions are needed to integrate wood's renewable and regenerative potential into the Horizon Europe programme 2028–2034. These decisions should encompass fundamental, applied, demonstrative, innovative and educational approaches, and emphasise their synergies. Wood science, technology, and engineering, as part of the wider bioeconomy domain, with links to sustainable forestry and related value chains, must be explicitly included in the new FP10. It is essential that breakthrough knowledge, innovation, and deployment are carried out in close collaboration with society.

Policy Brief
January 2026

Contribution of WoodPoP to the Advanced Materials Act Consultation

The European Wood Policy Platform (WoodPoP) plays a strategic role in shaping framework conditions for sustainable wood-based value chains and in developing evidence-based policy solutions, measures, and recommendations. By fostering dialogue among policymakers, industry, and research, the platform drives innovation and strengthens wood's contribution to climate change mitigation, supporting Europe's transition towards a clean, just, and competitive economy. The needs of the sector to strengthen the wood-based circular bioeconomy are summarised in the Policy Paper "A Wood-Based Circular Bioeconomy for a Sustainable Europe".

The European Wood Policy Platform (WoodPoP) welcomes the initiative on the Advanced Materials Act and calls for targeted measures to ensure that renewable bio-based materials—particularly wood—are explicitly recognised as advanced materials.

Wood is an essential raw material for Europe's green transition, generating climate benefits, enabling circularity, and fostering strategic autonomy. Its multifunctionality, renewability, and ability to substitute fossil-based and carbon-intensive materials make it indispensable to Europe's industrial and climate strategies. It has high potential to support rural development due to the local raw material availability in the EU and to improve overall circularity and sustainability.

Wood as an advanced material supports all objectives of the Advanced Materials Act – increasing R&D activities, increasing production capacity and availability, improving circularity and sustainability, or the simplification of procedures.

Bio-based materials, like wood, clearly fall within the definition of advanced materials (as already mentioned in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the co-programmed European Partnership 'Innovative Advanced Materials for Europe' (IAM4EU), especially when modified or engineered for particular purposes to have new or improved functionalities. Bio-based materials are complex and have advantageous full-lifecycle impacts. These materials are independent of critical raw materials, allowing impacts to be felt quickly and definitively.

To fully leverage its potential, we recommend the inclusion of the following key priorities in the Advanced Materials Act:

- Explicit recognition and prioritisation of renewable bio-based materials as advanced materials, reflecting their essential role in achieving climate neutrality and circularity.
- Investment in European production capacity, with wood-based advanced materials prioritised as a means to strengthen supply chain resilience, reduce import dependencies, and enhance strategic autonomy.

Policy Brief
6 February 2026

Wood promotion as driver of Europe's green transition: Insights from WoodPoP

The European Wood Policy Platform (WoodPoP) is a pan-European initiative that brings together policymakers and stakeholders across the wood value chain. It aims to support the development of sustainable, wood-based bioeconomy policies in Europe through dialogue, knowledge exchange, and joint policy recommendations. WoodPoP emphasises that wood strategies and promotion programs are key political instruments for achieving goals relating to climate, the circular bioeconomy, the housing crisis (affordable housing), and rural development. These programmes are designed to be technology-neutral and in alignment with the EU's internal market and regulations of the member states, including state aid regulations. In line with the European Green Deal, Clean Industrial Deal, the EU Forest Strategy, and emerging EU carbon storage policies, as well as the EU Competitive Compass, these programmes support the transition to climate-friendly construction, the use of wood for long-lasting applications, and the development of circular value chains. Furthermore, a new EU Bioeconomy Strategy focuses on scaling up innovations, creating market demand for bio-based products, ensuring sustainable biomass supplies from sustainable sources, and boosting rural jobs. Wood as a bio-based construction product is emphasised as a key enabler.

The strategic role of wood in European, national and regional climate policies

When used in long-life products, wood stores biogenic carbon over the relevant service lifetime of the products and can replace more carbon-intensive, fossil-based materials, such as steel, concrete, and plastics, e. g., in buildings and infrastructure. This reduces the total GHG emissions associated with the manufacturing of products. Under the LULUCF framework and related methodological guidance, the change in the carbon stocks in sawn wood, timber panels, and other bio-based construction products in buildings is taken into account to estimate CO₂ emissions and removals in harvested wood products, in addition to the forest carbon stock changes.

Prioritising wood for long-lasting applications like in buildings will substantially improve the carbon balance of the harvested wood products pool, even if harvest levels remain constant. As highlighted by recent research, studies on demand trends in the construction sector up to 2070 suggest that higher adoption of engineered wood products could deliver emissions savings of up to 50% compared to business-as-usual scenarios¹. National schemes such as Norway's Wood Grants explicitly utilise this logic by incentivising farmers to use wood for new livestock buildings, thereby reducing emissions from the building stock while maintaining productive agriculture.

When appropriately designed, these schemes can fall within the scope of compatible environmental aid under EU state aid rules, as they support objectives of common European interest, namely climate mitigation, while ensuring proportionality, avoiding overcompensation, and minimising distortions of competition, in line with Article 107(3)(c) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). The activities of the WoodPoP are exemplary models for fulfilling the social, cultural, and educational responsibilities of public institutions while pursuing the ambitious objectives set out in

¹ <https://www.fao.org/forestry/newsroom/news-detail/wood-products-in-focus-new-fao-findings-highlight-wood's-role-in-climate-action-and-bioeconomy-at-wcte-2023/en>

Position paper
22 April 2026

WoodPoP¹ Policy Recommendations for the Revised General Block Exemption Regulation (GBER)

Enabling Wood-Based Solutions for Europe's Green Transition

This paper presents WoodPoP's policy contribution to the revision of the General Block Exemption Regulation (GBER), highlighting the strategic role of wood and wood-based sectors in Europe's climate transition and industrial competitiveness, as set out in WoodPoP's Policy Paper². It advances implementation-focused proposals to promote renewable construction materials and reinforce wood-based value chains, in line with the objectives of affordable housing, climate neutrality and the principles of the New European Bauhaus.

The wood and wood-based sectors are at the core of Europe's green transition

The wood and wood-based sectors are among the key industries that will enable the transition to a climate-neutral European economy. By supplying renewable, low-carbon materials for construction and related applications, they make a direct contribution to sustainability, resource efficiency and bioeconomy, while also generating significant benefits in terms of workforce development, job creation, income generation and the advancement of circularity.

The wood-based construction and wood processing industries are of particular importance due to their innovative capacity, their contribution to rural development and urbanisation, coupled with their ability to deliver practical solutions at scale. Within these sectors, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) constitute the predominant share of economic actors. However, these companies often have limited administrative capacity and are highly sensitive to regulatory complexity and investment risk.

For this reason, WoodPoP recommends that the sustainable use of locally sourced, renewable materials in construction should be recognised as an activity of common European interest. Such recognition would more accurately reflect the strategic importance of wood in Europe's green transition and contribute to unlocking investment across the sector.

Key elements of the revised GBER that require stronger emphasis

WoodPoP commends the European Commission's efforts to streamline state aid regulations, alleviate administrative burdens, and foster the adoption of simplified cost options. These measures represent significant progress towards establishing a more accessible and effective framework for businesses and public authorities.

¹ <https://woodpop.eu/>

² <https://woodpop.eu/resources/wood-policy-paper/>

Available at woodpop.eu
E-Mail us at contact@woodpop.eu

WoodPoP Dara Award

WoodPoP Dara Award

Celebrating Sustainable Timber Construction

Hall of Fame

- All valid submissions will be featured on the webpage
- This dedicated space will showcase outstanding timber projects, celebrate innovation, inspire timber adoption, and honor excellence in wood construction

Categories

- Residential buildings
- Non-residential buildings
- Infrastructure
- Renovation, expansion projects and/or build-on-top

Dara Award

Physical Trophy

WoodPoP Dara Award

Winning design

WoodPoP
DARA AWARD

Julie Kratěnová

- ❖ **Inspired by the Celtic Dara knot**
- ❖ Materials: **oak and glass**
- ❖ The **glass element** represents **the Czech glassmaking tradition**
- ❖ Evokes a wooden structure made of two parts joined by a single connection
- ❖ Author: Julie Kratěnová, Faculty of Architecture

WoodPoP Dara Award

Participation

22 countries

59 submitted
projects

22 Judges
representing countries

Save the date

**1ST DARA AWARD
CEREMONY**

**26
NOV
2026**

Prague, Czechia

Global developments and processes

- **Initiated by Austria supported by Australia, Japan, Türkiye, FAO, IUFRO and UNFFS, to....**
 - **develop** the forest-based bioeconomy worldwide
 - foster the **sustainable use** of forest products
 - promote sustainable production and consumption
 - **strengthen the global dialogue** on wood solutions and other forest-based bioeconomy approaches
 - exchange and uplift the spirit of **forest-based cooperation**
- **Highlights**
 - **Global Webinar Series** (Lead by FAO supported by AT&FIN)
 - Six webinars to different topics within forest-based bioeconomy approaches
 - Output: recordings, summary reports, recommendations (final report)
 - **Science Policy Briefs**
 - For the six topics of the thematic sessions
 - Lead by IUFRO
 - **Global Summit**

Global Summit „Advancing Sustainable Forest-based Bioeconomy Approaches”,

23-25 February 2026 in Vienna, Austria

Co-chaired by Austria and South Africa

Outcomes

- **Vienna Call for Action** for a sustainable forest-based bioeconomy
- **Co-Chairs' Summary** (with recommendations)
 - Presentation at **UN Forum on Forests (UNFF21)** and
 - **FAO's 28th Committee on Forestry (COFO28)**

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Participants at the COLI Summit

- over 60 countries
- over 100 organizations

WoodPoP at COLI

Upcoming meetings

Upcoming WoodPoP meetings:

- **9th EGM, 15 September 2026**, online 10:00 – 12:00 CET
- Fifth HLM and **Dara Award Ceremony**, 26 November 2026, Prague, CZ
- Prologue V (**Innovation**), 2 December 2026, Innsbruck, AT
- Other meetings of interest:
 - Innovawood General Assembly 5.-7. May 2026 Tulln, Vienna AT
 - UNFF 21, 11 – 15 May 2026 New York City, USA
 - 28th Session of the Committee on Forestry FAO 28 September – 2 October 2026, Rome IT

Engage with WoodPoP

- **SIGN-UP** for a technical working group
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- **SUBSCRIBE** to our newsletter and stay updated

<https://woodpop.eu/>

Thank you!

contact@woodpop.eu

www.woodpop.eu

**WoodPoP Secretariat,
International Union of Forest Research
Organizations (IUFRO)**

National and International Wood Policy

5 May 2026

Dr. Georg Rappold

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Environmental Protection, Regions and Water Management,
Republic of Austria